

SorBET: STEM learning through interactive classification

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"SorBET" (Sorting Based on Educational Technology), is a novel digital educational authoring tool, designed to enhance learning experiences. With an intuitive interface, real-time feedback, and collaborative gameplay using webcam tracking, SorBET aims to provide an immersive and adaptable learning environment tailored to teachers and children's needs and interests. In this paper, we will discuss the affordances of this tool, drawing on preliminary pilot experiments that have been conducted so far.

Classification • Embodied Learning • Computational Thinking •

1 INTRODUCTION

A significant amount of educational research has investigated the effectiveness of digital educational games in cultivating 21st-century skills and promoting collaboration among students (Gee, 2003). By engaging players in challenging scenarios and presenting them with authentic problems to solve, digital games provide opportunities for students to practice critical thinking and analytical reasoning, while also developing content knowledge in a multidisciplinary context. One key aspect highlighted in research is the development of collaboration skills within these environments (Squire & Jenkins, 2003). Traditional teaching methods often struggle to captivate young learners, leading to disconnection and limited retention of knowledge. To address these challenges and foster collaboration alongside critical thinking, we design an online educational tool called "SorBET"¹. SorBET is a digital educational tool that allows playing, modifying and designing classification games from scratch (Grizioti & Kynigos, 2024). It was designed by the Educational Technology Laboratory of NKUA, to function as a game generator but also to expose students, besides being players, to the active role of the game designer. In SorBET games, objects "fall from the sky" and the player should use quick decision-making to correctly classify them in the category boxes at the bottom of the screen (Figure 1). Instant feedback indicates the accuracy of their classifications, reinforcing learning outcomes for the embedded concepts. SorBET integrates two high-level computational affordances, an interactive database and block-based programming, that allow students and teachers, without prior programming knowledge, to develop digital classification games of any content (Figure 2). In the design mode of SorBET, users can modify what is considered right and wrong, the objects that will fall, how inclusive or distinctive the categories will be, and how fast and how many objects will fall at once. This feature allows students to question the game content and express their own perceptions on the topic. Moreover, it enables them to easily adapt the game content to any possible topic enhancing multidisciplinary approaches such as STEM. SorBET was recently extended to support AR in the form of interacting with game objects through gesture recognition (Mrlard et al. 2023). This

¹ <http://etl.ppp.uoa.gr/sorbet/>

allows for two students to play simultaneously using their body movements and develop their communication skills in their classroom environment.

Figure 1: Two SorBET games in play mode: On the left, the player classifies mathematical angles as depicted on pictures, on the right the player classifies everyday objects and materials according to the time needed for their degradation.

Figure 2: The Design Mode of SorBET integrating an interactive database for designing the game objects, categories and classification model, and block-based programming for other game rules.

2 APPLICATION IN STEM LEARNING

SorBET's versatility extends to various STEM subjects, from basic animal classes to complex socio-cultural topics like feelings or cultural diversity. For instance, in Figure 1 are two SorBET games embedding different concepts from STEM subjects. This breadth of exploration is further enhanced by the game's unique "doubt factor". By introducing ambiguity into classifications, SorBET encourages critical thinking and ignites a curiosity to delve deeper into the subject matter. This aligns perfectly with the core principle of STEM education: inquiry-based learning (Crippen & Archambault, 2012). SorBET fosters a spirit of curiosity through this "doubt factor," mirroring the iterative problem-solving approach prevalent in STEM fields. Players grapple with uncertain classifications, prompting them to question and explore, a process essential for success in STEM research.

By allowing users to manipulate game content and parameters using a high-level database and the Blockly code environment, learners are also encouraged to develop essential skills like algorithmic thinking, data analysis, and problem-solving - essential skills in both STEM and real-world contexts. Moreover, the interconnection between computational thinking and the core STEM subjects of Science, Engineering, and Mathematics is evident in SorBET's design. Players participate in an activity that mimics the iterative problem-solving methodology common in STEM subjects by modifying game variables and creating personalized classification games. In addition to solidifying theoretical ideas, this hands-on experience gives students the ability to recognize the real-world applications of computational thinking in a variety of fields. Just as important is the collaboration aspect. Effective STEM education emphasizes collaboration and communication as essential skills for success in today's interconnected world. SorBET facilitates collaborative learning experiences through its multiplayer mode, where two players can work together to classify objects in real-time. By encouraging teamwork, negotiation, and peer-to-peer communication, SorBET aims to develop the interpersonal skills necessary for effective collaboration in STEM-related projects and endeavors.

3 PRELIMINARY STUDIES AND FINDINGS

The openness of the SorBET thematic environment has allowed for multifaceted research, both in terms of subject areas, such as mathematics (Kynigos, et al., 2023) or ancient Greek, but also in terms of specific skills (Grizioti & Nikolaou, 2023; Grizioti & Kynigos, 2024).

In a study focusing on classification and mathematical thinking, two mathematical classification games were designed within the SorBET platform, each focusing on different mathematical concepts (Kynigos, et al., 2023). The rationale behind having these two games was to explore the development of student classification processes in varied contexts and to gain insight into their mathematical meaning-making. The 'Numbers' game engaged students in classifying falling numbers into categories such as 'Real', 'Rational', and 'Integer', aiming to make abstract mathematical concepts tangible and relatable. Meanwhile, the 'Falling Angles' game focused on classifying objects based on their angles, drawing from real-life contexts and challenging traditional abstract representations found in textbooks. The study, conducted in an experimental middle school in Greece, involved six students aged 13–14 with limited gaming experience but basic mathematical knowledge. Through game modding activities, where students played and then modified the games, researchers observed the development of students' classification processes and mathematical meaning-making. The analysis revealed how students progressed from initial strict categorization to more flexible classification criteria, leading to deeper mathematical understanding. Additionally, the process of modding the activities sparked unexpected ideas, such as creating sub- and overarching categories for geometrical shapes, showcasing students' engagement in mathematical processes beyond the intended scope of the games.

Another study by Grizioti & Kynigos (2023), aimed to explore new dimensions of student engagement with computational thinking (CT), specifically focusing on data practices and critical CT. Organized as part of a larger ongoing design-based research project, involving six students aged 13-14 in an after-school mathematics and STEM club. Over two 2-hour sessions, students worked in randomly formed pairs, first playing, and then modifying two classification games: "Falling Angles" from a different point of view; and "App Game". Data collection involved various methods such as screen and audio recordings, student worksheets, observation notes, and semi-structured interviews. Through qualitative thematic analysis, the researchers identified four key themes: (1) development data practices and CT, (2) game data model refinement and design, (3) pattern recognition and abstraction practices, and (4) classification and critical thinking. Notably, students developed strategies for data interpretation, classification, and game modification, demonstrating critical engagement with game content and structure.

After the enhancement of the software with hand recognition feature, a pilot study examined how middle school students develop classification skills through SorBET as a collaborative game. Students used hand gestures to classify objects like mobile apps into subjective categories, sparking discussions and debates about the most fitting classification. Researchers observed a deepened understanding of classification concepts like comparing objects and including or excluding them from categories. The embodied interaction using hand gestures seemed to facilitate communication and collaboration among students. Through engaging with the tool, students explored classification concepts such as comparison, inclusion, and exclusion while actively manipulating categories and entities. The embodied interactions facilitated by the tool played a crucial role in enhancing expression, meaning-making, and collaboration in a tangible manner. These initial findings suggest that digital embodied classification tools hold promise in promoting higher-order classification processes and fostering collaborative learning experiences among students. Further research and refinement of the tool are necessary to fully realize its potential in educational settings.

Figure 4, Students engage with SorBET's hand recognition.

The studies carried out so far are initial stages of larger and more in-depth investigations. The exploitation of the new additions to the digital tool will provide a new dimension to the research and learning process, through the involvement of emerging technology which allows the active collaboration of more players and the possibility of greater engagement with the game's functionalities through block programming.

DISCUSSION

The preliminary studies on SorBET highlight its potential to enhance critical thinking, collaboration, and subject-specific knowledge acquisition within STEM education, particularly in areas such as mathematics and classification skills. The incorporation of a "doubt factor" encourages curiosity and inquiry, aligning with the principles of inquiry-based learning. Additionally, features like co-design capabilities and multiplayer mode with embodied interaction foster essential collaboration, communication, and negotiation skills vital for effective teamwork in STEM fields. These findings contribute to the growing research on digital educational games and their role in developing 21st-century skills. Further investigation into SorBET's effectiveness in diverse learning contexts is warranted, including large-scale studies across different grade levels and subjects, longitudinal studies to assess long-term effects, and exploration of integration with existing curricula. By continuing to explore Sorbet's potential, we can advance the development of engaging and impactful digital tools for promoting collaboration, critical thinking, and deeper understanding in STEM education.

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